

IN SILICO EVALUATION OF *SOLIVA SESSILIS* PHYTOCHEMICALS TARGETING KEY PROTEINS INVOLVED IN DIABETIC WOUND HEALING

^{*1}Mnahil Gamal, ²Dr. Mohammed S. Eltoum and ²Dr. Mai Makki

^{*1}Kassala University College of Education, Department of Chemistry and Biology.

²Sudan University of Science and Technology College of Science, Chemistry Department.

***Corresponding Author: Mnahil Gamal**

Kassala University College of Education, Department of Chemistry and Biology.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18151946>

How to cite this Article: ^{*1}Mnahil Gamal, ²Dr. Mohammed S. Eltoum, and ²Dr. Mai Makki (2026). In Silico Evaluation Of Soliva Sessilis Phytochemicals Targeting Key Proteins Involved In Diabetic Wound Healing. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Science, 12(1), 141–148.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 05/12/2025

Article Revised on 25/12/2025

Article Published on 01/01/2026

ABSTRACT

Diabetic wounds represent a major clinical challenge due to impaired angiogenesis, persistent inflammation, and dysregulated extracellular matrix remodeling. This study aimed to evaluate, through an in-silico approach, the binding interactions of selected phytochemicals from *Soliva sessilis* with key proteins involved in wound healing. Methylhexadecanoate, hexadecenoic acid and octadecanoic acid were docked against vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), tumor necrosis factor -alpha (TNF- α), and collagenase using Auto-Dock 4. Docking results revealed favorable binding affinity and stabilizing interactions between the phytochemicals and the target proteins. Methylhexadecanoate exhibited the strongest binding affinity toward collagenase. These findings suggest that constituents of *Soliva sessilis* may promote wound healing by modulating angiogenesis, inflammation, extracellular matrix remodeling. Further in vivo validation is recommended.

KEYWORDS: *Soliva sessilis*, diabetic wound healing, molecular docking, collagenase, VEGF, TNF- α .

INTRODUCTION

Diabetic wounds exhibit delayed healing due to chronic inflammation, impaired vascularization, and oxidative stress. Hyperglycemia at the wound site disrupts the healing cascade, leading to diminished growth factor production, and excessive protease activity.^[1, 2]

The global interest in medicinal plants has surged due to their bioactive compounds with diverse pharmacological activities.^[3] Secondary metabolites are produced within plants, which are of great pharmacological importance having differences in molecular structure and their properties.^[4]

Wound healing is a complex process involving a number of interdependent and overlapping stages including hemostasis, inflammation proliferation, vascularization and production of matrix and remodeling.^[5] Many types of cells are involved in each phase of wound healing including immune cells, endothelial cells, keratinocytes,

and fibroblasts which undergo marked changes in gene expression and phenotype.^[6,7] One aspect of diabetic healing that has recently received considerable attention the enhanced and prolonged expression of Tumor Necrosis Factor Alpha (TNF- α), a potent proinflammation cytokine.^[8,9] Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) affects on multiple components of the wound healing cascade, including angiogenesis and epithelization and collagen deposition.^[10] Collagenase is believed to be important for cell migration and collagen remodeling during tissue repair and regeneration.^[11]

Molecular docking has become an essential aspect of in-silico drug development in recent years.^[12] This technique involves predicting the interaction between a small molecule and a protein at atomic level.^[13] This enables researchers to study the behavior of small molecules, such as nutraceuticals, within the binding sites of a target protein and understand the fundamental biochemical processes underlying this interaction.^[14]

The ligand-receptor complex's computational electrostatics can be assessed, screened and predicted through the docking study, as stated by Sahoo *et al.*^[13]

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Selection and Preparation of Ligands

The chemical constituents of *Soliva sessilis* identified via GC-MS analysis namely Methylhexadecanoate, Hexadecenoic acid, and Octadecanoic acid were selected for this study. The 3D structures of these ligands were drawn using Avogadro - 1.2 and subsequently converted to PDBQT format using Auto Dock Tools (ADT). Energy minimization was performed to ensure the most stable conformation for docking.

Preparation of Target Proteins

The three-dimensional crystal structures of the target proteins: Tumor Necrosis Factor-alpha (TNF- α , PDB ID: 2AZ5), Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF, PDB ID: 1VPF), and Collagenase (PDB ID: 1CGL) were retrieved from the RCSB Protein Data Bank. The

proteins were prepared by removing co-crystallized ligands and water molecules. Missing atoms were fixed, and Kollman charges and polar hydrogen atoms were added using Auto Dock Tools.

Molecular Docking Protocol

Docking was performed using Auto-Dock 4 with the Lamarckian Genetic Algorithm (LGA) with default parameters, and the number of GA runs was set to 20 for each ligand protein complex. The grid box was centered on the active site of each protein. Grid dimensions were adjusted to encompass the entire active site.

Visualization and Interaction Analysis

Docking interactions were visualized using PyMOL (3D) and Discovery Studio (2D). The best-scoring poses were selected based on binding energy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 summarizes the binding affinities and key interacting residues for each ligand-protein complex.

Table 1: Docking Scores and Binding Energies.

Ligand	Target Protein	Binding Energy (kcal/mol)	Key Interacting Residues
Octadecanoic acid	2AZ5	-3.64	TyrB:119, TyrB:59, TyrB:151, GlyA:121, Leu A:57
Hexadecenoic acid	2AZ5	-3.72	TyrB:119, TyrB:59, TyrB:151, GlyA:121, LeuA:57
Methylhexadecanoate	2AZ5	-3.03	TyrB:119, TyrB:59, TyrB:151, GlyA:121, LeuA:57
Octadecanoic acid	1VPF	-2.98	LysA:48, MetA:31, ProA:53, ProA:49, ValB:20, TyrB:21, MetB:13, PheB:17.
Hexadecenoic acid	1VPF	-2.21	SerB:24, MetA:31, ProA:49, ValB:20, TyrB:21, PheB:17, MetB:13.
Methylhexadecanoate	1VPF	-2.63	ProA:49, LysA:48, MetA:43, MetB:13, TyrB:21, PheB:17.
Octadecanoic acid	1CGL	-3.95	GlyB:172, TyrA:240, GluA:172, LeuA:131, ProA:235
Methylhexadecanoate	1CGL	-6.12	GlyB:172, TyrA:240, TyrA:131, GlyA:212, ProA:233

Methylhexadecanoate exhibited the moderate to favorable binding affinity toward collagenase (1CGL), with a binding energy of -6.12 kcal/mol, stabilized by hydrogen bonding with Gly172, and Glu172, and several van der Waals contacts with Pro233.

Octadecanoic acid showed favorable binding with collagenase (1CGL) with a binding energy of -3.95 kcal/mol. The interaction involved the ligand carboxylic group forming hydrogen bonds with Gly172, and Glu172, as well as hydrophobic contacts with Leu131.

Hexadecenoic acid displayed a moderate binding score of -3.72 kcal/mol with TNF- α . Its interaction was primarily hydrophobic, involving residues such as Tyr119 and Tyr59, indicating potential anti-inflammatory activity.

Overall, the docking score suggests that methylhexadecanoate is the most promising compound's for modulating collagenase activity. In diabetic wounds, collagenase is often overexpressed, leading to excessive extracellular matrix degradation and delayed healing. By

binding to collagenase, methylhexadecanoate may help reduce this hyperactivity allowing for more controlled tissue remodeling. This modulation could promote fibroblast migration, re-epithelialization and granulation tissue formation, ultimately support wound closure. In addition, the compounds hydrophobic and anti-inflammatory properties may contribute to creating a favorable healing environment.

Visualization of Ligand-Protein Interactions

To better understand the binding modes of phytochemicals from *Soliva sessilis* with key proteins involved in diabetic wound healing poses were visualized using PyMOL (3D) and Discovery Studio (2D). The best binding conformations (those with the lowest binding energies) were selected for each ligand-target complex.

Octadecanoic Acid Interactions

With TNF- α (2az5)

Molecular docking of octadecanoic acid with TNF- α , was further analyzed through 3D and 2D interaction visualization. The 2D interaction diagram in Figure 1

(A), binding occurs via van der Waals and pi-Alkyl interactions. One unfavorable interaction was observed.

The 2D interaction diagram in Figure 1 (B), supports a low to moderate binding affinity.

Figure 1: Molecular interactions of octadecanoic acid with TNF- α (PDB ID:1az5).

(A) 3D binding pose.

(B) 2D interaction diagram.

(B)

With collagenase (1cgl)

In Figure 2(A), octadecanoic acid is well accommodated in the pocket with a hydrogen bonds Tyr240, Glu212,

and Gly172 as well as hydrophobic contacts. Figure 2(B) supports the strong binding potential through multiple favorable contacts.

Figure 2: Molecular interactions of octadecanoic acid with collagenase (PDB ID: 1cgl).

(C) 3D binding pose.

(D) 2D interaction diagram.

With VEGF (1vpf)

Octadecanoic acid fits within the VEGF site (Figure 3A), with hydrophobic interactions with Pro53 and Pro46.

The 2D diagram (Figure 3B) shows no hydrogen bonds but good surface complementarity.

Figure 3: Interaction of octadecanoic acid with VEGF (PDB ID: 1vpf).

(E) 3D binding pose.

(F) 2D interaction diagram.

Methylhexadecanoate Interactions

With collagenase (1cgl)

Figure 4 (A), shows methylhexadecanoate occupying the collagenase binding groove. A hydrogen bond with Tyr240, Tyr131 and several hydrophobic contacts (Figure 4 B) suggest possible modulation of matrix degradation.

Figure 4: Molecular interaction of methylhexadecanoate with collagenase (PDB ID: 1cgl).

(G) 3D binding pose.

(H) 2D interaction diagram.

With TNF- α (2az5)

As shown in Figure 5 (A), the ligand mainly forms hydrophobic interactions with Try119, Try59, and Try151, with no strong hydrogen bonds. The 2D plot

(Figure 5 (B)) shows pi-alkyl contacts, suggesting a moderate affinity that could modulate TNF-mediated inflammation.

Figure 5: Molecular interaction of methylhexadecanoate with TNF- α (PDB ID: 2az5).

(A) 3D binding pose.

(B) 2D interaction diagram.

(B)

With VEGF (1vpf)

Among the three ligands, methylhexadecanoate showed a relatively balanced interaction with VEGF although its

binding strength may be slightly limited by steric interference due to an unfavorable donor-donor contact as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Molecular interaction of methylhexadecanoate with VEGF (PDB ID: 1vpf).

- (A) 3D binding pose.
- (B) 2D interaction diagram.

(A)

(B)

Hexadecanoic Acid Interactions

With TNF- α (2az5)

In Figure 7 (A) hexadecanoic acid binds the surface groove of TNF- α , forming limited hydrogen bonds with Gly121, and Tyr151. The 2D interaction map Figure 7 (B) reveals a combination of pi-alkyl and alkyl interactions which may slightly reduce binding stability.

These visual interaction maps confirm the docking results, showing that all three ligands engage key residues in their respective protein targets. The differences in bonding types (hydrogen, hydrophobic, van der Waals) help explain the variability in binding scores and predicted biological roles, suggesting that *Soliva sessilis* phytochemicals may contribute synergistically to diabetic wound healing via angiogenesis promotion, inflammation control, and matrix regulation.

CONCLUSION

The present *in silico* study demonstrates that selected phytochemicals from *Soliva sessilis* exhibit favorable interactions with VEGF, TNF- α , and collagenase, suggesting their potential role in modulating key pathways involved in diabetic wound healing. Among the evaluated compounds methylhexadecanoate showed the most promising interaction profile, particularly against collagenase. These findings support the potential of *Soliva sessilis* as a source of bioactive compounds for wound healing applications.

REFERENCE

- Petel, S., Srivastava, S., Singh, M. R., Singh, D. Mechanistic insight into diabetic wound: Pathogenesis, molecular targets and treatment strategies to pace wound healing. *Biomed. Pharmaceutics*, 2019; 15: 281.
- Blakytyny R and jude E. The molecular biology of chronic wounds and delayed healing in diabetes. *Diabetic Medicine*, 2006; 23(6): 594-608.
- Bijauliya RK, Alok S, Singh M, Mishra SB. Morphology, Phytochemistry and Pharmacology of *Syzygium cumini* (Linn.) - an overview. *Int J Pharm Sci Res*, 2017; 8(6): 2360-2371.
- Sunita Arora and Ganesh Komar, Phytochemical Screening of root, stem and leaves of *Cenchrus biflorus* Roxb. *Journal of pharmacognosy and phytochemistry*, 2018; 7(1): 1445-1450.
- Reinke J.M. and Sorg H, Wound repair and regeneration. *European Surgical Research*, 2012; 49(1): 35-43.
- Tellacha L. E., Veves A. A. and Carvalho E. Inflammatory and angiogenic abnormalities in diabetic wounds healing: role of neuropeptides and therapeutic perspectives. *The open Circulation and Vascular Journal*, 2010; 3: 43-55.
- Singer J. and R. Clark A. F., Cutaneous wound healing. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 1999; 341(10): 738-746.
- Valluru M, Station C. A., Reed M. W. Transforming growth factor- β and endoglin signaling orchestrate wound healing. *Frontiers in physiology*, 2011; 2: 89.
- Xu F and Zhang C. Abnormal cell Responses and Role of TNF- α in impaired Diabetic wound healing. *BioMed Research International*, 2013; 10: 9.
- Philip Bao, Arber K, Marjana T. C, Micheal S. G. H, Paul. E. and Harlod B. The Role of vascular Endothelial Growth Factor in wound Healing. *J. Surg. Res*, 2009; 153(2): 347-358.
- Magnus S. A, Carolyn. L. T. Frederick. W. J. William H. E. and Patricia M. M. Collagenase in wound healing: Effect of wound age and type. *Journal of Investigative Dermatology*, 1992; 99: 709-714.
- Agu P. C, Afiukwa C. A., Orji O. U, Ezeh E. M., Ofoke I. H., Ogbu C. O., Ugwuja E. I. and Aja P. M. Molecular docking as a tool of the discovery of molecular targets of nutraceuticals in diseases management. *Nature*, 2023; 13: 1398.
- Sahoo, R. N. Pattanak, S. Pattnaik, G. Mallick, S., and Mohapatra, R. Review on the use of molecular docking as the first line tool in drug discovery and development. *Indian J. Pharm. Sci*, 2022; 84(5): 1334-1337.
- Smyth, M. S. and Martin J. H. Xray crystallography. *Mol. Pathol*, 2000; 53: 8-14.